

Table 2. Performance of Jalaprabha in national trials in India. 1989-94.

Year	Trial ^a /site	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Maximum water depth (cm)
		Jalaprabha	Jalamagna	
1989	PVT6			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.9 ^b	nil	65
	North Lakhimpur, Assam	2.1 ^b	1.2	110
1990	IVT-DW			
	Pusa, Bihar	2.5	2.4	na ^c
	North Lakhimpur, Assam	4.1 ^b	2.6	na
1991	AVT-DW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.8 ^b	0.5	95
	Pusa, Bihar	3.4 ^b	2.2	na
1992	AVT-DW			
	Motto, Orissa	2.4	1.7	125
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	3.7	2.7	141
1993	AVT-DW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.6 ^b	0.6	100
1994	AVT-DW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	4.0 ^b	0.9	80
	Pusa, Bihar	3.8 ^b	2.5	na
	Motto, Orissa	2.8 ^b	2.4	na

^aPVT 6 = preliminary variety trial 6, IVT-DW = initial variety trial-deepwater, AVT-DW = advanced variety trial-deepwater. ^bSignificantly superior to national check at the 5% level. ^cna = not available.

Both alkali value (6.5) and amylose content (30.0) are high.

Saraswati has resistance to blast, sheath blight, sheath rot, yellow stem borer, and whitebacked planthopper.

Jalaprabha was developed by pedigree selection from a composite cross sent by IRRI and evaluated as IET11870 in the national varietal testing program for several years (Table 2). The pooled

averages across 12 locations yielded 73% more than check Jalamagna. The variety's yield potential is 4.1 t ha⁻¹. In national testing, it ranked second in the 1990 initial variety trial-deepwater, first in the 1991 advanced variety trial-deepwater, third in the 1993 advanced trial-deepwater, and first in the 1994 advanced variety trial-deepwater. The All-India Rice Workshop in 1995 recommended it for the eastern Indian states of West Bengal, Orissa, Bihar, and Uttar Pradesh.

Jalaprabha is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and flowers around the first week of November. Its submergence tolerance is mainly through elongation, and it has very good kneeing ability. Panicles are compact and well exerted with short, bold, golden grains. Kernels are about 5.6 × 2.4 mm. Hulling percentage is 78.8 and milling percentage is 64.1. Both alkali value (7.0) and amylose content (29.2) are high. Seed dormancy is about 3 mo.

It has tolerance for yellow stem borer, leaffolder, sheath rot, sheath blight, blast, and false smut. ■

Seed technology

Nucleus and breeder seed production of thermosensitive genic male sterile lines

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Thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines are suitable for developing two-line hybrids in the tropics because temperature variations are found in different seasons and/or locations for maintaining effective sterility and fertility. Research efforts by IRRI and national agricultural research systems (NARS) have resulted in identifying many TGMS lines from four to five sources that can be deployed for developing two-line hybrids. Production of good-quality

pure seed of TGMS lines is a prerequisite for successful use of these lines.

Experience in China has indicated that TGMS lines multiplied conventionally by bulking their seeds at a fertility-inducing temperature may tend to segregate for their critical sterility /fertility points. Seed obtained from such lines may not be pure. These lines, when used to produce two-line hybrid seeds, could be a mixture of selfed and hybrid seeds, resulting in unstable hybrids. Nucleus and breeder seed production strategies should, therefore, aim to meet the dual objectives of maintaining complete male sterility during hybrid seed production and higher seed set during TGMS multiplication. We describe here a simple method of producing nucleus

and breeder seed of TGMS lines under field conditions.

Seasons / locations suitable for TGMS multiplication and hybrid seed production must be identified based on weather data and the behavior of selected TGMS lines. For example, at IRRI, flowering of TGMS lines in January and February induces fertility and is ideal for multiplication, whereas flowering from mid April to May induces complete male sterility, a condition necessary for hybrid seed production. The proposed method shown in the figure will produce nucleus and breeder seed of TGMS lines.

Nucleus seed production of a TGMS line is initiated in a fertility-inducing environment. Seeding of TGMS lines is

Procedure for nucleus and breeder seed production of TGMS lines.

arranged so that the sensitive stage occurs when the temperature is favorable for higher seed set. At flowering, about 100 typical plants are selected from the population of a TGMS line and their panicles are bagged. The selection process is completed within a week. After harvest, selected plants are scored for spikelet fertility (based on the main panicle) and 50 plants with higher spikelet fertility are selected.

Progenies of the selected plants are grown in the sterility-inducing environment. About 30 seeds are taken from each of the selected plants to grow single row progenies and the remaining seed is stored carefully. Progenies that are uniform and completely male sterile are marked. The balance seeds of such selected progenies (stored earlier) are bulked to form the nucleus seed (see figure).

Nucleus seed is used to produce breeder seed under strict isolation. Breeder seed is produced in the fertility-inducing environment. The whole process of producing nucleus seed is repeated from the breeder seed plot. Fresh breeder seed should be used by seed production agencies to produce foundation seed of TGMS lines. The latter should be used to produce hybrid seeds. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management — inorganic sources

Response of promising rice genotypes to N levels in rainfed lowlands

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Rainfed lowlands in India constitute about 17 million ha, which is about 40% of the total rice area. Rice varieties selected for their nutrient require-

ments, particularly N, have great relevance for boosting overall production of rainfed lowland rice in India.

The performances of genotypes IET12199, IET10664, IET8655, IET12777, and IET5914 were compared with that of local check Gayatri at three N levels (0, 40, and 80 kg ha⁻¹).

The soil was sandy clay loam (Haplustalf), with a pH of 5.6, 0.40% organic C, and 230 kg available N ha⁻¹ (Kjeldahl method), 17 kg available P

ha⁻¹ (NH₄F extraction), and 280 kg available K ha⁻¹ (NH₄OAc extraction). The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design at CRLRRS with the genotypes in the main plot and N in the subplots with four replications.

Forty-five-day-old seedlings of different genotypes were transplanted during the first week of August. The recommended doses of 17.6 kg P ha⁻¹ and 16.6 kg K ha⁻¹, along with one-third of the N according to the treatment,